

ANALYSIS OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF CLEANING SEEDS WITH COMPLETE FIBER SEPARATION.

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Abstract: Although researchers have conducted analyzes on the issue of improving the productivity of the equipment in the technological process of cleaning seeds with complete separation of fiber, but this issue has not been fully resolved, the article gives opinions on quality separation of fiber.

Keywords: Fiber, fluff, light industry, export, linter, construction, regenerators.

Although researchers have conducted analyzes on the issue of improving the productivity of the equipment and product quality in the technological process of cleaning seeds with complete separation of fibers, but this issue has not been fully resolved. It is known that after the linting process, the fluff contains a large amount of impurities, which leads to a decrease in the quality of the products obtained from it. Taking into account that the cleaning process is complicated and the cleaning efficiency is low, it is possible to reduce the amount of impurities in the lint produced by cleaning the seed before the linting process. There is little or no scientific research on cleaning the seed after the ginning process.

Some of the foreign compounds in cotton are added to the fiber during the ginning process, and some are added to the seeds and pollute them.

Seeds after germination may contain sand, small dirt, leaves, and metal objects. In addition, in the mass of seeds, there are also small, poorly developed, immature seeds. These are crushed and crushed during various processes and lead to increased lint and seed contamination. In addition, there are also seeds whose fiber has not been completely extracted, and by sorting them, it is possible to increase the output of fiber.

Taking into account the importance of quality indicators in the next technological process for the processing of ginned hairy seeds, in addition, taking into account the introduction of new cotton varieties with specific physical and mechanical properties into production in recent years, the fractional composition of hairy seeds under production conditions is determined. studies were conducted for the purpose of learning.

Cotton fiber produced in our republic is exported to many countries of the world, including USA, Greece, Russia, England, South Korea, Italy, Germany, Holland, Japan and others.

Currently, starting from 2020, 100% of the cotton fiber produced in our country will be reprocessed and exported as a finished product. In the world market, special attention is paid to the whiteness of the fiber, the degree of contamination, and especially the micronaire index. If the micronaire index is higher than 4.8-4.9, the fiber is considered coarse and cannot compete in the world market. The purchase price of coarse fiber is also low. The main and acceptable indicator for determining the price of cotton fiber is its relative breaking strength of 23.5-26.4 gk/tex.

Therefore, the quality of the fiber depends not only on the selection scientists and growers, but also on the proper organization of the work of the processing enterprises and their adherence to standard requirements. That is, in the production of high-quality fiber, along with its natural quality indicators (length, color, thickness, ripening, etc.), the installation of the correct technological process in processing cotton, and the technical condition of the machines used in it are of particular importance. It can be said that the use of well-maintained, well-adjusted machines in the technology, the modes of operation of the working bodies, the technological intervals are set correctly, guarantees the production of quality products.

Although researchers have conducted analyzes on the issue of improving the productivity of the equipment and product quality in the technological process of cleaning seeds with complete separation of fibers, but this issue has not been fully resolved. It is known that after the linting process, the fluff contains a large amount of impurities, which leads to a decrease in the quality of the products obtained from it. Taking into account that the cleaning process is complicated and the cleaning efficiency is low, it is possible to reduce the amount of impurities in the lint produced by cleaning the seed before the linting process. There is little or no scientific research on cleaning the seed after the ginning process.

Therefore, today it is appropriate to carry out scientific research on the improvement of seed cleaning techniques and technology, to ensure the efficient and high-quality production of fiber, lint, and seed.

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not been completely extracted, and by sorting them, it is possible to increase the output of fiber. Taking into account the importance of quality indicators in the next technological process for the processing of ginned hairy seeds, in addition, taking into account the introduction of new cotton varieties with specific physical and mechanical properties into production in recent years, the fractional composition of hairy seeds under production conditions is determined. studies were conducted for the purpose of learning. Cultivation of cotton raw materials, separation of fiber from residual hairy seed (linting), production and supply of quality fiber is the basis of the national economy. For this reason, he studied foreign techniques and technologies of linters in depth, based on achievements and experiences.

Improving existing linters and increasing their efficiency is one of the urgent tasks in our republic. Improvement of technique and technology in cotton linting, including obtaining high-quality lint, is one of the main problems. That's why scientific research on obtaining high-quality fluff by completely separating the seed and improving the quality of linter is of particular importance. After the ginning process, a certain amount of mostly short fiber remains on the surface of the seed. These fibers are called fluff. The fluff is extracted by "scraping" from the surface of the seed. The harvesting machine is called a linter. The length of the fluff is from 6 mm to 26 mm. If the length of the fiber is shorter than 6 mm, then it is called hair. And the hair is separated in special hair separator - delinter machines.

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